

Derivative Pricing and Credit Valuation Adjustment

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a theory for credit valuation adjustment (CVA). Based on our theory, we propose a novel cash-flow-based practical framework for calculating the bilateral risky value and bilateral CVA at the counterparty portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong/right way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong/right way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

Key Words: credit value adjustment (CVA), credit risk modeling, financial derivative valuation, collateralization.

In this paper, we present generic models for valuing defaultable financial derivatives. For completeness, our study covers various cases: unilateral and bilateral, single payment and multiple payments, positive and negative payoffs. Although a couple of simple cases have been studied before by other authors, e.g. Duffie and Singleton (1999), Duffie and Huang (1996), who only provide heuristic derivations in a non-rigorous manner; analytic work on the other cases is novel. In contrast with the current recursive integral solution (see Duffie and Huang (1996)), our theory shows that the valuation of defaultable derivatives in most situations requires a backward induction procedure.

There is an intuitive way of understanding these backward induction behaviours: We can think that any defaultable derivative with bilateral credit risk embeds two default options. In other words, when entering a defaultable financial transaction, one party grants the other party an option to default and, at the same time, also receives an option to default itself. In theory, default may occur at any time. Therefore, default options are American style options that normally require a backward induction valuation.

We explicitly indicate that, within the context of risky valuation, the market value of a defaultable derivative is actually a risky value rather than a risk-free value, because a firm may default at any future time even if it survives today. An intuitive explanation is that after charging the upfront CVA, one already converted the market value of a defaultable derivative from the risk-free value to the risky value.

From a practical perspective, we propose a novel framework to perform the bilateral risky valuation and calculate the bilateral CVA at a portfolio level, which incorporates netting and margin (or collateral) agreements and captures wrong/right way risk.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Basic setup is provided in Section 1; pricing unilateral defaultable derivatives and their unilateral CVAs is discussed in Section 2; valuing bilateral asymmetric defaultable derivatives and their bilateral CVAs is elaborated on in Section 3; a practical framework that embraces netting agreements, margining agreements, and wrong/right way risk is proposed in Section 4, and the numerical results are presented in Section 5. The conclusions are given in Section 6.

1. Basic Setup

We consider a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P})$ satisfying the usual conditions, where Ω denotes a sample space, \mathcal{F} denotes a σ -algebra, \mathcal{P} denotes a probability measure, and $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denotes a filtration.

The default model is based on the reduced-form approach proposed by Duffie and Singleton (1999) and Jarrow and Turnbull (1994), which does not explain the event of default endogenously, but characterizes it exogenously by a jump process. The stopping (or default) time τ is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default with a stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity $h(t)$.

It is well-known that the survival probability, conditional on a realization path, from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$S(t, s) := \Pr(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (1a)$$

where Z is the firm-specific state process that helps forecast that firm's default. The default probability, conditional on the realization path, for the period (t, s) in this framework is defined by

$$Q(t, s) = \Pr(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z) = 1 - S(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (1b)$$

Applying the law of iterated expectations, we express the expected survival probability for the period (t, s) as

$$\bar{S}(t, s) = E\left[\exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (2a)$$

where $E\{\bullet \mid \mathcal{F}_t\}$ is the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t . The expected default probability for the period (t, s) is expressed as

$$\bar{Q}(t, s) = 1 - \bar{S}(t, s) = 1 - E\left[\exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (2b)$$

There are three different recovery models in the literature. The default payoff is either 1) a fraction of par, 2) a fraction of an equivalent default-free bond, or 3) a fraction of market value. We use the recovery model of market value in our study.

The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. For a discrete one-period (t, s) economy, at the end of the period a defaultable derivative either defaults with the default probability $Q(t, s)$ or survives with the survival probability $S(t, s)$. The risky value of the derivative, conditional on the realization path, is the discounted expectation of the payoffs, given by

$$V^D(t) = D(t, s) \left(Q(t, s) \varphi(s) V^D(s) + S(t, s) V^D(s) \right) \quad (3a)$$

where

$$D(t, s) = \exp \left[- \int_t^s r(u) du \right] \quad (3b)$$

where $D(t, s)$ denotes the stochastic risk-free discount factor at t for the maturity s and $r(u)$ denotes the risk-free short rate at time u ($t \leq u \leq s$).

For risk-free valuations, the market value is a risk-free value, but for risky valuations, the market value is actually a risky value. An intuitive explanation is that one already converted the market value from the risk-free value to the risky value after charging the upfront CVA.

2. Unilateral CVA

Two parties are denoted as A and B . The unilateral credit risk assumes that only one party is defaultable and the other one is default-free. In this section, we assume that party A is default-free, whereas party B is defaultable. All calculations are from the perspective of party A . Let the valuation date be t . We study single payment cases first.

2.1. Single Payment Cases

Consider a defaultable derivative that promises to pay a X_T from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T . The payoff X_T may be positive or negative, i.e. the derivative may be

either an asset or a liability to each party. The risk-free value of the derivative at valuation date t is given by

$$V^F(t) = E\{D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (4)$$

where $D(t, T)$ is the risk-free discount factor defined in (3b).

We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

Proposition 1: *The unilateral risky value of the single payment derivative is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{C_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (5a)$$

where

$$C_B(t, T) = \exp\left[-\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} c_B(t + i\Delta t)\Delta t\right] \quad (5b)$$

$$c_B(t + i\Delta t) = r(t + i\Delta t) + 1_{V^D(t+(i+1)\Delta t) \geq 0} h_B(t + i\Delta t)(1 - \varphi_B(t + i\Delta t)) \quad (5c)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise.

We may think of $C_B(t, T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor and $c_B(u)$ as the risk-adjusted short rate. Here $\varphi_B(u)$ represents the default recovery rate of party B , and $h_B(u)$ represents the hazard rate of party B . $s_B(u) = h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u))$ is called the credit spread or the short credit spread.

In theory, a default may happen at any time. The Continuous-Time Risky Valuation Model, or simply the Continuous-Time Model (CTM), assumes that a defaultable derivative is continuously defaultable. Proposition 1 can be further expressed in the form of the CTM as:

Corollary 1.1: *The unilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{\bar{C}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (6a)$$

where

$$\bar{C}_B(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T \bar{c}_B(u) du\right] \quad (6b)$$

$$\bar{c}_B(u) = r(u) + 1_{V^D(u) \geq 0} h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (6c)$$

The proof of this corollary becomes straightforward, according to Proposition 1, by taking the limit as Δt approaches zero.

Proposition 1 provides a general form for pricing a unilateral defaultable single payment derivative. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that the payoff X_T is non-negative, we derive the following corollary:

Corollary 1.2: *If the payoff X_T is non-negative, the risky value of the single payment derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{\widehat{C}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (7a)$$

where

$$\widehat{C}_B(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T \widehat{c}_B(u) du\right] \quad (7b)$$

$$\widehat{c}_B(u) = r(u) + h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (7c)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to (6) by setting $V^D(u) \geq 0$. Since the payoff X_T is non-negative, the intermediate value $V^D(u)$ is also non-negative.

Equation (7) is the same as Equation (10) in Duffie and Singleton (1999). In their heuristic derivation, the authors implicitly treat the market value of a defaultable derivative as a risky value because the market price therein evolves in a defaultable manner. Otherwise, they would not have been able to obtain the desired result.

By definition, the corresponding CVA of the single non-negative payment derivative can be expressed as

$$CVA^U(t) = V^F(t) - V^D(t) = E\{D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} - E\{\widehat{C}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (8)$$

Since $\widehat{C}_B(t, T)$ is always smaller than $D(t, T)$, the CVA is, in this case, a credit charge. The credit charge covering party A 's potential loss comes from the scenario of party B 's default when party A is in the money in the portfolio.

The Discrete-Time Risky Valuation Model, or simply the Discrete-Time Model (DTM), assumes that a defaultable derivative may only default on payment dates.

Proposition 2: *The unilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E[G_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (9a)$$

where

$$G_B(t, T) = D(t, T)[1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0} Q_B(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))] \quad (9b)$$

The corresponding unilateral CVA of the single payment derivative under the DTM can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} CVA^U(t) &= V^F(t) - V^D(t) = E\{D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} - E\{G_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \\ &= E[1_{X_T \geq 0} D(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))Q_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) shows that if the payoff is in the money, the CVA is a credit charge equal to the discounted potential loss. If the payoff is out of the money, the CVA is zero.

Proposition 2 has a general form that applies in a particular situation in which we assume that the payoff X_T is non-negative.

Corollary 2.1: *If the payoff X_T is non-negative, the risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E[\overline{G}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (11a)$$

where

$$\overline{G}_B(t, T) = D(t, T)[1 - Q_B(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))] = D(t, T)(S_B(t, T) + \varphi_B(T)Q_B(t, T)) \quad (11b)$$

The proof of this corollary is straightforward according to Proposition 2 by setting $X_T \geq 0$. Equations (11) are consistent with equations (3).

2.2. Multiple Payments Cases

Suppose that a defaultable derivative has m cash flows. Any of these cash flows may be positive or negative. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_1, \dots, X_m with payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m . The risk-free price of the derivative is given by

$$V^F(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\{D(t, T_i)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (12)$$

We divide any payment date period (T_{i-1}, T_i) into n_i very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

Proposition 3: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[(C_B(t, T_i)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t]\right] \quad (13a)$$

where

$$C_B(t, T_i) = \exp\left[-\sum_{j=0}^{\sum_{k=1}^i n_k - 1} c_B(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t\right] \quad (13b)$$

$$c_B(t + j\Delta t) = r(t + j\Delta t) + 1_{V^D(t+(j+1)\Delta t) \geq 0} h_B(t + j\Delta t)(1 - \varphi_B(t + j\Delta t)) \quad (13c)$$

If we model default in a continuous-time setting, the Proposition 3 can be further expressed as follows.

Corollary 3.1: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\bar{C}_B(t, T_i)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right)\right] \quad (14)$$

where

$$\bar{C}_B(t, T_i) = \exp\left[-\int_t^{T_i} \bar{c}_B(u)du\right] \quad (14b)$$

$$\bar{c}_B(u) = r(u) + 1_{V^D(u) \geq 0} h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (14c)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained, according to Proposition 3, by taking the limit as Δt approaches zero.

Proposition 3 has a general form that applies in a particular situation in which we assume that all the payoffs are non-negative.

Corollary 3.2: *If all the payoffs are non-negative, the risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\widehat{C}_B(t, T_i) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (15a)$$

where

$$\widehat{C}_B(t, T_i) = \exp\left[-\int_t^{T_i} \widehat{c}_B(u) du\right] \quad (15b)$$

$$\widehat{c}_B(u) = r(u) + h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (15c)$$

The proof of this corollary is straightforward, according to (14), by setting $V^D(u) \geq 0$.

If we assume that a default may occur only on the payment dates, the result is the following proposition in a discrete-time setting.

Proposition 4: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} G_B(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (16a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$G_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - 1_{(X_{j+1} + V^D(T_{j+1})) \geq 0} Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}))\right] \quad (16b)$$

Proposition 4 has a general form that applies in a particular situation where we assume that all payoffs are non-negative.

Corollary 4.1: *If all the payoffs are non-negative, the risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} \overline{G}_B(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (17a)$$

Where $t = T_0$ and

$$\overline{G}_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}))\right] \quad (17b)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to Proposition 4 by setting $(X_{j+1} + V^D(T_{j+1})) \geq 0$.

3. CVA Implementation

The risky valuation theory described above can be applied to any defaultable derivatives. In this section, we develop a practical framework to demonstrate how to perform the risky valuation and how to calculate the bilateral CVA at a portfolio level. The framework incorporates netting and margin agreements and captures right/wrong way risk. We use the DTM as an example. Switching to the CTM is quite straightforward, but requires more granular simulation time steps, e.g. daily.

Two parties are denoted as A and B . All calculations are from the perspective of party A . Let the valuation date be t . The risky valuation and CVA computation procedure consists of the following steps.

4.1. Risk-Neutral Monte Carlo Scenario Generation

One core element of a counterparty credit risk management system is the Monte Carlo scenario generation (market evolution). This must be able to run a large number of scenarios for each risk factor with flexibility over parameterization of processes and treatment of correlation between underlying factors. Credit exposure may be calculated under a real probability measure, while CVA may be conducted under a risk-neutral probability measure.

4.2. Cash Flow Generation

For ease of illustration, we choose a vanilla interest rate swap as an example. For most banks, interest rate swaps account for more than half of their derivative business.

Assume that party A pays a fixed rate, while party B pays a floating-rate. We are considering that fixed rate payments and floating-rate payments occur at the same payment dates and with the same day-count conventions, and ignoring the swap funding spread. Though the generalization to different payment dates, day-count conventions and swap funding spreads is straightforward, we prefer to present a simplified version to ease the notation.

Assume that there are M time buckets (T_0, T_1, \dots, T_M) in each scenario, and N cash flows in the sample swap. Let us consider scenario j first.

For swaplet i , there are four important dates: the fixing date $t_{i,f}$, the starting date $t_{i,s}$, the ending date $t_{i,e}$ and the payment date $t_{i,p}$. In general, these dates are not coincidently at the simulation time buckets. The time relationship between swaplet i and the simulation time buckets is shown in Figure 1.

4.2.1. Cash Flow Determination

The cash flow of swaplet i is determined at the fixing date $t_{i,f}$, which is assumed to be between the simulation time buckets T_j and T_{j+1} . First, we need to create an interest rate curve, observed at $t_{i,f}$, by interpolating the interest rate curves simulated at T_j and T_{j+1} via either Brownian Bridge or linear interpolation. Then, we can calculate the payoff of swaplet i at scenario j as

$$\chi_{j,i} = N \left(F(t_{i,f}; t_{i,s}, t_{i,e}) - R \right) \delta(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e}) \quad (27)$$

where N denotes the notional, $F(t_{i,f}; t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$ denotes the simply compounded forward rate reset at $t_{i,f}$ for the forward period $(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$, $\delta(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$ denotes the accrual factor or day count fraction for the period $(t_{i,s}, t_{i,e})$, and R denotes the fixed rate.

4.2.2. Cash Flow Allocation

The cash flow amount calculated by (27) is paid on the payment date $t_{i,p}$. This value should be allocated into *the nearest previous time bucket* T_k as:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{j,k,i} = \chi_{j,i} D(T_k, t_{i,p}) \quad (28)$$

where $D(T_k, t_{i,p})$ denotes the risk-free discount factor based on the interest rate curve simulated at T_k .

Cash flow generation for products without early-exercise provision is quite straightforward. For early-exercise products, one can use the approach proposed by Longstaff and Schwartz (2001) to obtain the optimal exercise boundaries, and then the payoffs.

4.3. Aggregation and Netting Agreements

After generating cash flows for each deal, we need to aggregate them at the counterparty portfolio level for each scenario and at each time bucket. The cash flows are aggregated by either netting or non-netting based on the netting agreements.

For netting, we add all cash flows together in the same scenario and at the same time bucket to recognize offsetting. The aggregated cash flow under netting at scenario j and time bucket k is given by

$$\tilde{\chi}_{j,k} = \sum_i \tilde{\chi}_{j,k,i} \quad (29a)$$

For non-netting, we divide cash flows into positive and negative groups and add them separately. In other words, offsetting is not recognized. The aggregated cash flows under non-netting at scenario j and time bucket k are given by

$$\tilde{\chi}_{j,k} = \begin{cases} \sum_l \tilde{\chi}_{j,k,l} & \text{if } \chi_{j,k,l} \geq 0 \\ \sum_m \tilde{\chi}_{j,k,m} & \text{if } \chi_{j,k,m} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (29b)$$

4.4. Margin (or Collateral) Agreements

Assume that the collateral margin period of risk is ς . The collateral methodology consists of the following procedures:

First, for any time bucket T_k , we introduce an additional collateral time node $T_k - \varsigma$. Second, we compute the portfolio value $V_j^F(T_k - \varsigma)$ at scenario j and collateral time node $(T_k - \varsigma)$. Then, we calculate the collateral required to reduce the exposure at $(T_k - \varsigma)$ as

$$\Gamma_j(T_k - \varsigma) = \begin{cases} V_j^F(T_k - \varsigma) - H_B, & \text{if } V_j^F(T_k - \varsigma) \geq H_B \\ 0, & \text{if } H_A < V_j^F(T_k - \varsigma) < H_B \\ V_j^F(T_k - \varsigma) - H_A, & \text{if } V_j^F(T_k - \varsigma) \leq H_A \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

where $H_B = TH_B + MTA_B$ is the collateral threshold of party B and $H_A = -(TH_A + MTA_A)$ is the negative collateral threshold of party A .

Each bank has its own collateral simulation methodology that simulates the collateral value evolving from $\Gamma_j(T_k - \varsigma)$ to $\Gamma_j(T_k)$ over the margin period of risk ς . The details of collateral simulation are beyond the scope of this paper. Assume that the collateral value $\Gamma_j(T_k)$ has already been calculated.

Next, we compute the change amount of the collaterals between T_k and T_{k-1} as

$$\Delta\Gamma_{j,k} := \Delta\Gamma_j(T_k) = \Gamma_j(T_k) - \Gamma_j(T_{k-1}) \quad (31)$$

Since our CVA methodology is based on cash flows, we model collateral as a reversing cash flow $-\Delta\Gamma_{j,k}$ at T_k . Finally, the total cash flow at T_k is given by

$$\bar{\chi}_{j,k} = \tilde{\chi}_{j,k} - \Delta\Gamma_{j,k} \quad (32)$$

4.5. Wrong or Right Way Risk

Wrong way risk occurs when exposure to a counterparty is adversely correlated with the credit quality of that counterparty, while right way risk occurs when exposure to a counterparty is positively correlated with the credit quality of that counterparty. For example, in wrong way risk, exposure tends to increase when counterparty credit quality worsens, while in right way risk, exposure tends to decrease when counterparty credit quality declines. Wrong/right way risk, as an additional source of risk, is rightly of concern to banks and regulators.

To capture wrong/right way risk, we need to correlate the credit quality (credit spreads or hazard rates) with other market risk factors, e.g. equities, commodities, etc., in the scenario generation.

4.6. CVA Calculation

After aggregating all cash flows via netting and margin agreements, one can price a portfolio in the same manner as pricing a single deal. We assume that the reader is familiar with the regression-based Monte

Carlo valuation model proposed by Longstaff and Schwartz (2001) and thus do not repeat some well-known procedures for brevity.

4.6.1. Risk-Free Valuation

We first calculate the risk-free present value of a counterparty portfolio. The risk-free value at scenario j is given by

$$V_j^F(t) = \sum_{k=1}^m \bar{\chi}_{j,k} D(t, T_k) \quad (33a)$$

The final risk-free portfolio value is the average (expectation) of all scenarios given by

$$V^F(t) = E(V_j^F(t)) = E\left(\sum_{k=1}^m \bar{\chi}_{j,k} D(t, T_k)\right) \quad (33b)$$

4.6.2. Risky Valuation

The risky valuation procedure is performed iteratively, starting at the last effective time bucket T_m , and then working backwards towards the present. We know the value of the portfolio at the final effective time bucket, which is equal to the last cash flow, i.e. $V_j^D(T_m) = \bar{\chi}_{j,m}$.

Based on the sign of $V_j^D(T_m)$ and Proposition 8, we can choose a proper risk-adjusted discount factor. The discounted cash flow at T_{m-1} is given by

$$\Psi_{j,m-1} = Y_j(T_{m-1}, T_m) V_j^D(T_m) = Y_j(T_{m-1}, T_m) \bar{\chi}_{j,m} \quad (34a)$$

where

$$Y_j(T_{m-1}, T_m) = D_j(T_{m-1}, T_m) \left(1_{V_j^D(T_m) \geq 0} y_{j,B}(T_{m-1}, T_m) + 1_{V_j^D(T_m) < 0} y_{j,A}(T_{m-1}, T_m) \right) \quad (34b)$$

where $y_{j,B}(T_{m-1}, T_m)$ and $y_{j,A}(T_{m-1}, T_m)$ are defined in (25).

Let us go to the penultimate effective time bucket T_{m-1} . The risk-adjusted discount factor has a switching type, depending on the sign of $V_j^D(T_{m-1}) + \bar{\chi}_{j,m-1}$, where $V_j^D(T_{m-1})$ is the value of the portfolio excluding the current cash flow $\bar{\chi}_{j,m-1}$ at scenario j and time bucket T_{m-1} . Note that $V_j^D(T_{m-1})$ is not the discounted cash flow, but rather the expectation of the discounted cash flow conditional on the market

states. We can use the well-known regression approach proposed by Longstaff and Schwartz (2001) to estimate $V_j^D(T_{m-1})$ from cross-sectional information in the simulation by using least squares. After estimating $V_j^D(T_{m-1})$, we can express the discounted cash flow at T_{m-2} as

$$\Psi_{j,m-2} = Y_j(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1})Y_j(T_{m-1}, T_m)\bar{\chi}_{j,m} + Y_j(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1})\bar{\chi}_{j,m-1} \quad (35a)$$

where

$$Y_j(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1}) = D_j(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1}) \left(1_{(\bar{\chi}_{j,m-1} + V_j^D(T_{m-1})) \geq 0} y_{j,B}(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1}) + 1_{\bar{\chi}_{j,m-1} + V_j^D(T_{m-1}) < 0} y_{j,A}(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1}) \right) \quad (35b)$$

where $y_{j,B}(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1})$ and $y_{j,A}(T_{m-2}, T_{m-1})$ are defined in (25).

Assume that in the previous step T_i , we estimated the portfolio value $V_j^D(T_i)$. Now, we proceed to T_{i-1} . The discounting switch-type depends on the sign of $V_j^D(T_i) + \bar{\chi}_{j,i}$. The discounted cash flow at T_{i-1} is given by

$$\Psi_{j,i-1} = \sum_{k=i}^m \left(\prod_{l=i-1}^{k-1} Y_j(T_l, T_{l+1}) \right) \bar{\chi}_{j,k} \quad (36)$$

We conduct the backward induction process, performed by iteratively rolling back a series of long jumps from the final effective time bucket T_m across time nodes until we reach the valuation date. Then, the present value at scenario j is

$$\Psi_{j,0} = \sum_{k=1}^m \left(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} Y_j(T_i, T_{i+1}) \right) \bar{\chi}_{j,k} \quad (37a)$$

The final true/risky portfolio value is the average (expectation) of all scenarios, given by

$$V^D(t) = E(\Psi_{j,0}) = E \left[\sum_{k=1}^m \left(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} Y_j(T_i, T_{i+1}) \right) \bar{\chi}_{j,k} \right] \quad (37b)$$

CVA is by definition the difference between the risk-free portfolio value and the true (or risky or defaultable) portfolio value given by

$$CVA^B(t) = V^F(t) - V^D(t) = E \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^m \left[\left(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} D_j(T_i, T_{i+1}) \right) \bar{\chi}_{j,k} - \left(\prod_{i=0}^{k-1} Y_j(T_i, T_{i+1}) \right) \bar{\chi}_{j,k} \right] \right\} \quad (38)$$

6. Conclusion

This article presents a theory for pricing defaultable financial derivatives and their CVAs. First, we want to indicate that the market value of a defaultable derivative is actually a risky value rather than a risk-free value. In fact, in applying the upfront CVA, we already converted the market value of a defaultable derivative from the risk-free value to the risky value.

For completeness, our theoretical study covers various cases. We find that the valuation of defaultable derivatives and their CVAs, in most situations, has a backward recursive nature and requires a backward induction valuation. An intuitive explanation is that two counterparties implicitly sell each other an option to default when entering into a defaultable transaction. If we assume that a default may occur at any time, the default options are American style options. If we assume that a default may only happen on the payment dates, the default options are either European options or Bermudan options. Both Bermudan and American options require backward induction valuations.

Based on our theory, we propose a novel cash-flow-based practical framework for calculating the bilateral risky value and bilateral CVA at the counterparty portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong/right way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong/right way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

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